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COMPARATIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF DUAL ANTIPLATELET THERAPY VERSUS MONOTHERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE

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ANNOTATION

This article highlights the difference between efficiency of dual antiplatelet therapy and antiplatelet monotherapy in 60 patients with ischemic stroke.

Keywords: ischemic stroke, dual antiplatelet therapy, monoantiplatelet monotherapy, good outcome, poor outcome.

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ИШЕМИК ИНСУЛЬТ ЎТКАЗГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА ИККИ ЁҚЛАМА АНТИАГРЕГАНТ ТЕРАПИЯ ВА МОНО АНТИАГРЕГАНТ ТЕРАПИЯНИНГ ҚИЁСИЙ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола 60 та биринчи марта ишемик инсулт ўтказган беморларда икки ёқлама антиагрегант терапия ва моно антиагрегант терапиянинг қиёсий самарадорлигини баҳолаш натижаларини ёритади.

Калит сўзлар: ишемик инсулт, икки ёқлама антиагрегант терапия, моно антиагрегант терапия, яхши прогноз, ёмон прогноз.

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СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ДВОЙНОЙ АНТИАГРЕГАНТНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ И МОНО АНТИАГРЕГАНТНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ С ИШЕМИЧЕСКИМ ИНСУЛЬТОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлены различия между эффективностью двойной антиагрегантной и моноантиагрегантной терапии у 60 пациентов с ишемическим инсультом.

Ключевые слова: ишемический инсулт, двойная антиагрегантная терапия, моноантиагрегантная терапия, хороший прогноз, плохой прогноз.

Introduction. Stroke is one of the leading causes of death and disability globally [1, 2]. It is associated with significant economic consequences [14]. Reduced mortality and morbidity are attainable only with effective treatment of ischemic stroke [7]. Ischemic stroke (IS) results from the abrupt loss of blood flow to a portion of the brain. The loss of blood flow to the brain could be due to thrombotic or embolic obstruction of a cerebral artery. Ischemic stroke is more frequent than hemorrhagic stroke [6]. There is an urgent need for improvements in secondary prevention to lower the risks of recurrence or mortality within five years after a first stroke [13, 14]. Cohort studies have revealed a decrease in the risk of recurrent stroke and transient ischemic (TIA) attacks with advancement in secondary stroke prevention measures [9]. Antiplatelet therapy is a crucial preventive intervention against stroke recurrence, ensuing vascular problems, and death [4, 8, 10]. The most widely utilized medications include aspirin, clopidogrel, and combinations of antiplatelet therapy like aspirin and clopidogrel. Following a stroke, single antiplatelet medicines have a well-established

role, and their use has been supported by several substantial research. Dual antiplatelet therapy (DAPT) use after an ischemic stroke is more debatable and has recently been proven useful in certain situations. Although early studies of chronic DAPT in stroke showed no additional benefit and increased bleeding over single antiplatelets, DAPT with aspirin and clopidogrel was found to help treat coronary artery disease [5, 11]. However, recent research indicates that DAPT may reduce stroke risk more than a single antiplatelet therapy because it more effectively inhibits platelet activation pathways. In contrast, clinical trials comparing DAPT to single antiplatelet therapy for secondary prevention have not consistently demonstrated a decrease in recurrent stroke and frequently showed increases in the frequency of bleeding [3]. The use of DAPT can continue for 21 to 90 days following a mild stroke or TIA, according to the 2019 Guidelines for the Management of Acute Ischemic Stroke. After 90 days, it is unclear whether antiplatelet administration should continue as monotherapy or dual treatment. Additionally, there are still questions about the best antiplatelet

approach to deploy and if DAPT can be safely used on a larger patient group. [12]. This research compared the efficacy of DAPT, which uses aspirin and clopidogrel in combination, with antiplatelet monotherapy (AM).

Purpose of the study. To compare the effectiveness of aspirin clopidogrel dual antiplatelet therapy (DAPT) with aspirin antiplatelet monotherapy (AM) in patients with ischemic stroke.

Materials and methods. 60 patients who underwent first IS were divided into two groups to receive the prescribed treatment. As part of secondary prevention, it includes antihypertensive, nootropics, vasoactive drugs indicated to control risk factors for stroke. In this case, patients in the first group received only 75 mg of acetylsalicylic acid as an antiplatelet treatment for 90 days, while patients in the second group received 300 mg of clopidogrel and 75 mg of acetylsalicylic acid as a loading dose on the first day, 75 mg of clopidogrel and 75 mg in 2-22 day, followed by clopidogrel 75 mg alone until 90 days. The condition of the patients, functional recovery, as well as complications and the effectiveness of the treatment were compared in both groups after 90 days. Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) and National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) were used in order to assess the functional outcome in 3 months following the case of stroke in patients. The inadequate prognosis is described as mRS≥3. When the general characteristics of the patients in both groups were analyzed, it was found

that there was no significant difference in the age of the patients in the groups and the gender ratio between them. The average age of patients in the AM group was 63.36±7.25, while in the DAPT group this indicator was 64.12±8.34. 13 (43.3%) in the AM group and 14 (46.6%) in the DAPT group were female. In addition, there is no significant difference between the comorbid conditions of the patients in the groups. NIHSS score at admission was 10.42±3.54 for MAAT group and 10.64±4.12 for IAAT group. No significant difference was observed between previous antiplatelet therapy and stroke subtypes.

Results. The following results were obtained when the patients' condition was evaluated using the NIHSS and Rankin scales at baseline and after 3 months. In patients of group 1, the average value of the NIHSS scale was 10.42±3.54 in the acutest period of the disease, and it was 6.08±3.32 after 3 months. In the second group, these indicators were found to be 10.64±4.12 and 4.84±3.04, respectively.

When the functional status of the patients was evaluated by the Rankin scale, its average value was 3.67±1.09 in the first group, 3.70±1.08 in the second group, after 3 months it was 2.42±1.06 in the first group, and 2.04±0.86 in the second group (5.3- table). As shown in the table below, functional recovery at 3 months was significantly higher in patients receiving DAPT than in patients receiving AM (Table 1).

Table 1. Pre- and post-treatment dynamics of scales indicators in both groups of patients.

Scales	Periods	Indicators	
		AM	DAPT
NIHSS	1 day	10.42±3.54	10.64±4.12
	10 days	9.66±3.32	8.78±3.47
	3 months	7.84±2.94	6.26±3.04
mRS	1 day	3.67±1.09	3.70±1.08
	10 days	3.43±1.04	3.12±1.03
	3 months	2.86±1.06	2.04±0.86

The given figures below show the improvement in dynamics according to NIHSS and Rankin scale in both groups of patients.

Figure 1. Indicators of improvement in dynamics according to NIHSS during the observation period in groups

Figure 2. Indicators of improvement in dynamics according to mRS during the observation period in groups

According to the indicators of the NIHSS, 17.5% improvement in patients who received DAPT, and 7.3% improvement in patients received AM was noted. At the end of the follow-up the improvement of functional outcome was 41.2% in the DAPT group, and 24.7% in the AM group. According to the index of mRS, 15.6% improvement in the DAPT received patients, 6.53% improvement in the AM group was determined. After 3 months functional status was 44.9% better in the DAPT group and 22.07% in the AM group. These results reflect the

effectiveness of DAPT and a significant improvement in key parameters.

Evaluation of treatment efficacy and complications of AM and DAPT.

The purpose of using DAPT is a secondary prevention of stroke. In the group of patients who received different treatment methods, stroke complications were studied over a period of 3 months (Table 2).

Table 2. Frequency of occurrence of complications in DAPT and AM groups at a 3-month follow-up.

Complications	AM(n=27)		DAPT (n=29)		p
	abs	%	abs	%	
Good outcome	18	66.7	24	82.7	0.038
Poor outcome	9	33.3	5	17.2	0.032

Reccurrence of IS	4	14.8	2	6.9	0.03
Hemorrhagic stroke	0	0	0	0	
TIA	2	7.4	1	3.4	0.3
Miocardial infarction	1	3.0	0	0	0
Hemorrhagic complications	0	0	0	0	
Death (for any reason)	3	10	1	3	0.64

From the data given above, it can be concluded that the percentage of good outcome is increased in patients receiving DAPT, and the probability of recurrent ischemic stroke is reduced.

When coagulation hemostasis parameters are analyzed before and after treatment to evaluate the effectiveness of the antiplatelet therapy,

we can see that the hemostatic balance is disturbed with the increased activity of the hemostatic system in the acute period of ischemic stroke (Table 3).

Dynamics of coagulogram parameters before and after treatment in patients who received DAPT and AM

Indicators	AM		DAPT		Control group
	Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment	
aPTT	22,1±2,34	26,8±2,36*	22,3±2,18	30,2±3,32*	31,3±3,38
Prothrombin time (sec)	9,2±0,8	10,8±1,2*	9,1±0,7	12,1±0,8*	12,8±1,1
Prothrombin activity (%)	124,6±8,2	105,7±8,4*	123,8±8,2	91,6±7,2*	88,6±7,2
Fibrinogen(мг/дл)	416.2±51,8	336.2±26.4*	415.8±52,4	288.5±23.2*	226±45,4
Thrombotest(даража)	4,8±0,47	4,01±0,41*	4,9±0,56	5,3±0,59*	4,1±0,5

* - $p < 0,01$

After treatment, it was found that the activity of the anticoagulant system was significantly restored in patients who received DAPT, and its indicators were statistically different from those of patients who received AM (Table 3).

Conclusion. According to the up-to-date studies early treatment with DAPT has been shown to be beneficial in high-risk TIA and minor

ischemic stroke, although the benefit in moderate to severe stroke is uncertain. In this study, we found that DAPT was associated with a very low rate of sICH in patients with moderate and severe ischemic stroke too. In conclusion, we can say that DAPT is effective at preventing recurrent stroke and to improve functional prognosis.

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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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